

Prevalence And Determinants Of Risky Sexual Behaviour Among Students In Ignatius Ajuru University Of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the prevalence and determinants of risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional design. The population of the study comprised of students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. A sample size of 1200 respondents was used for the study. Multi-stage sampling method was used to select respondents. The instrument for the study was a semi-structured questionnaire. Collected data was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science version 25.0. The result was obtained using descriptive and inferential statistical tools including graphs, frequency, simple percentages and ANOVA to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State was 21.1%. The tested hypotheses showed a significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State based on peer pressure [$F(1, 1198) = 7.700$; $p = 0.005$], internet use [$F(5, 1198) = 13.048$; $p = 0.005$] and parents socioeconomic status [$F(1, 1198) = 65.233$; $p = 0.005$]. It was concluded that students need intervention strategies to enhance a healthy sexual behaviour. The study recommended amongst others that the Government through ministry of social welfare and ministry of health should develop sexuality education enhancement strategies and aimed at improving sexuality education knowledge among students through provision of appropriate approaches capable of influencing students positively in all matters related to human sexuality and reproductive health.

Keywords: prevalence, determinants, risky sexual behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Teenage risky sexual behaviour is a serious public health issue because it can result in a number of detrimental outcomes, including STIs, unwanted pregnancies, and emotional and psychological distress.

A population at high risk for participating in various types of risky sexual behaviour (RSB) is frequently thought to be university students. Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and unwanted pregnancies are among the health risks associated with these behaviours, which can include unprotected sex, having multiple sexual partners, and casual or "hook-up" encounters (American College Health Association [ACHA], 2023; Centres for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2021). Hence, understanding the scope of this issue and the factors that contribute to it is crucial for developing effective prevention and intervention strategies on college campuses.

The alarming prevalence of RSB among college students has been reported in a number of research. About 43.9% of students said they had engaged in sexual activity without a condom within the previous 30 days, according to a comprehensive poll done by the ACHA in 2019. Furthermore, in the previous 12 months, 22.3% of students said they had three or more sexual partners. These results are in line with earlier studies that have calculated that 20–40% of college students have several sexual partners in a single year (Kuperberg & Padgett, 2016).

This group also has a startlingly high rate of "hooking up," or casual sexual encounters. According to studies, between 60 and 80 percent of college students have engaged in casual intercourse, frequently without wearing any kind of protection (Garcia et al., 2012). Numerous detrimental consequences, such as an elevated risk of STIs, unwanted pregnancy, and psychological discomfort, have been connected to these hook-up behaviours (Kuperberg & Padgett, 2016).

The high prevalence of RSB among university students can be explained by a complex interaction of contextual, interpersonal, and individual factors (Vasilenko et al., 2015). Research has found that impulsivity, sensation-seeking, and a lack of knowledge about sexual health are among the psychological traits that are linked to increased RSB (Hoyle et al., 2010). Substance use, specifically the use of alcohol and illicit drugs, has also been identified as a significant contributor to RSB among university students, with studies consistently showing that drug and alcohol use is associated with a higher risk of unprotected sex, multiple partners, and casual sexual encounters (Kiene et al., 2019; Olmstead et al., 2013). At the interpersonal level, peer influences and social norms play a crucial role in shaping the sexual behaviors of university students. Perceived peer approvals of RSB, as well as direct peer pressure, have been shown to increase the likelihood of engaging in these behaviors (Randolph et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the environment and culture of the larger campus may also have a role in the occurrence of RSB. Contextual factors on student sexual behaviour include things like the availability of tools for sexual health, the perceived social norms surrounding casual sex, and the general "hookup culture" on college campuses (Lee et al., 2011; Bogle, 2018). Since RSB can have a number of detrimental effects on one's physical and mental health, its high incidence among college students is a serious public health problem. Concerning consequences linked to these behaviours include the possibility of long-term reproductive health problems, the spread of STIs, and unwanted births (CDC, 2021; Buhi et al., 2010).

However, university students are a population particularly vulnerable to engaging in risky sexual behaviors, which can have significant implications for their health and well-being. While the prevalence of these behaviors, such as unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, and casual sexual encounters, is well-documented (ACHA, 2019; CDC, 2021), it is crucial to understand the key factors that contribute to their occurrence. However, numerous studies have highlighted the influential role of peer pressure in shaping the sexual behaviors of university students. Perceived peer approval and norms regarding casual sex and unprotected intercourse have been consistently linked to an increased likelihood of engaging in these risky behaviors (Scholly et al., 2015; Randolph et al., 2017). University students often feel a strong desire to conform to their peers' perceived attitudes and behaviors, which can lead them to make decisions that compromise their sexual health. For example, a study by Scholly et al. (2015) found that university students who believed their peers were engaging in casual sex were more likely to participate in hook-ups and have multiple sexual partners. Additionally, research has shown that direct peer pressure, either through explicit encouragement or social ostracization, can further encourage RSB among this population (Randolph et al., 2017). Addressing the influential role of peers is, therefore, a critical component in understanding and addressing risky sexual behaviors on college campuses.

Therefore, the widespread use of the internet and how it permeates college students' lives has also been found to be a major factor in RSB. The normalisation of casual sexual encounters and the adoption of more permissive sexual attitudes have been connected to the ease with which sexual content, including pornography, may be accessed online (Braun-Courville & Rojas, 2019; Vandenbosch & van Oosten, 2017). Additionally, the popularity of dating and hookup apps has made it easier for college students to have casual sex, which may lead to more unprotected sex and multiple partners (Sevi et al., 2018). According to a study by Choi et al. (2016), using dating apps often was linked to a higher chance of reporting recent casual intercourse and irregular condom use. The anonymity and accessibility of the internet can also contribute to the development of online sexual behaviors, such as sexting and the exchange of explicit images, which have been linked to offline sexual risk-taking (Dir et al., 2013). Understanding and addressing the role of the internet and digital technologies in shaping the sexual behaviors of university students is crucial for developing effective prevention and intervention strategies. Once more, one factor that has been found to influence RSB is the socioeconomic position (SES) of a university student's parents. According to research, students from lower-SES households might be more likely to participate in risky sexual behaviours such having many partners and unprotected sex (Vasilenko et al., 2015; Cubbin et al., 2015). Numerous factors have been connected to RSB, such as higher rates of substance use, the perception of fewer opportunities in the future, and limited access to comprehensive sexual health education and resources (Cubbin et al., 2015; Vasilenko et al., 2015). Additionally, the stress and instability associated with lower SES backgrounds can contribute to impulsive decision-making and a greater susceptibility to peer influences, further increasing the risk of engaging in risky sexual behaviors (Hoyle et al., 2010). Addressing the socioeconomic disparities that contribute to RSB among university students is, therefore, a crucial component of developing holistic and equitable interventions. Ensuring that all students have access to comprehensive sexual health education, as well as the resources and support necessary to make informed and healthy decisions, is essential for promoting positive sexual health outcomes.

However, a person's belief systems, including their religious and cultural values, can also have a big impact on how they behave when they have sex. Students at universities who have more conservative or traditional views on gender roles and sexuality may be less likely to engage in RSB because these views tend to discourage premarital sex and emphasise abstinence (Auerbach et al., 2019), while students with more liberal or permissive views may be more likely to do so because they encourage a more open and exploratory approach to sexuality. However, it is important to note that the relationship between belief systems and RSB is complex and can be influenced by various other factors, such as peer norms, parental influence, and access to sexual health resources. Hence, developing educational programs and resources that can resonate with students from different belief systems may be an effective strategy for addressing this determinant of risky sexual behavior. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate prevalence and determinants of risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

METHODOLOGY

The research design is a descriptive cross-sectional study. The area of this study was Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The population of the study consisted of students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt. The sample size of 1200 was calculated using Cochran formular. A two stage sampling method was used in the study. The instrument for eliciting information for this study was a structured questionnaire titled Questionnaire on prevalence and correlates of risky sexual behaviour. The instrument was validated by the supervisor and three experts from the department of Human Kinetics Health and Safety Education for content, construct and face validity. Copies of the questionnaire were given alongside the objectives, research questions and null hypotheses to the aforementioned experts for moderation. The criticism, amendment and correction were used to draft the final copy of instrument. Hence the instrument was valid and used for the study. The reliability for this study employed a test retest method with few copies

of the instrument (20 copies) which was administered to students in the University of Port Harcourt and after two weeks, the same copies were re-administered because of their homogenous characteristics. The Reliability coefficient value of 0.80 was obtained using Pearson Products Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). Hence the instrument was reliable and adopted for the study. The questionnaire was administered with the help of research assistants which was done within two weeks interval following on the spot retrieval after completion. The research assistants were guided on how to respond to questions asked by the participants. The data collected were coded and analyzed using Statistical Products for Service Solution (SPSS) version 25.0). The result was obtained using descriptive and inferential statistical tools including graphs, frequency, simple percentages and ANOVA to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Fig 1: Prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Figure 1 shows the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The result showed that the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State was 21.1%.

Table 1: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showing significant difference in risky sexual behaviour students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State based on peer pressure

Sources of variance	Sum of squares	of Df	Mean sum of squares	F-value	p-value	Decision
Between group	1.776	1	1.776	7.700	0.005	Rejected
Within group	282.918	1198	.231			
Total	284.693	1199				

*Significant. P<0.05

Table 1 shows the One-Way ANOVA of significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State based on peer pressure [F(1, 1198) = 7.700; p = 0.005] as the p<0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State based on peer pressure was rejected.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showing significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State based on internet use

Sources of variance	Sum of squares	of Df	Mean sum of squares	F-value	p-value	Decision
Between group	3.504	5	3.701	13.048	.000	Rejected
Within group	281.189	1198	.230			
Total	284.693	1119				

* Significant. $P < 0.05$

Table 2 shows the One-Way ANOVA of significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State based on internet use [$F(5, 1198) = 13.048$; $p = 0.005$] as the $p < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State based on internet use was rejected.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showing significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State based on peer pressure

Sources of variance	Sum of squares	of Df	Mean sum of squares	F-value	p-value	Decision
Between group	27.382	2	13.691	65.233	.000	Rejected
Within group	257.311	1198	.210			
Total	284.693	1119				

*Significant. $P < 0.05$

Table 3 shows the One-Way ANOVA of significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State based on parents socioeconomic status [$F(1, 1198) = 65.233$; $p = 0.005$] as the $p < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State based on parents socioeconomic status was rejected.

DISCUSSION

The finding of the study showed that less than half of the population involved in risky sexual behavior. Hence, this indicates that there is risky sexual behaviour among students. The finding of the study is in keeping with that of Durowale et al. (2017), Tolera et al. (2017) and Addis et al. (2022) who all recorded the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among students. The finding of the study is also in consonant with the finding of Mengesha and Enguday (2019) whose finding supported that there is risky sexual behaviour among students. This is so because risky sexual behaviour is the order of the day amongst university students coupled with the decadence in moral values and norms in the society. This has been stated because in the university community today, risky sexual behaviour among students is no longer a new thing in the recent society. Therefore, the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among students will continue to increase from time to time. However, other factors such as age, gender, parental upbringing and peer pressure could play important roles in risky sexual behaviour among students.

The finding of the study showed that there was a significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students based on peer pressure. This showed that peer pressure contributes to risky sexual behaviour among students. The finding of the study is in keeping with the finding of Durowale et al. (2017) and that of Tolera et al. (2017). Their findings indicated that peer relationships were top in the risky sexual behaviour among students. The finding of the study is also similar with the studies of Eze et al. (2021) and Azeze et al. (2021) whose reported that risky sexual behaviour among students was associated with factors such as peer pressure. This is so because friends have more influence and control over their mates or those who associate with them. However, in other to feel belonged, most students or adolescents end

up practicing what is trending or obtainable amongst group of friends or peers. However, parental upbringing and other factors could also restrict students in involving in risky sexual behavior. However, as at the time of the present, no previous work was found to contradict the finding of the present study. However, more studies supported the fact the other circumstances in the decaying society and university system could play important roles in risky sexual behaviour among students.

The finding of the study showed that there was a significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students based on internet use. This showed that internet use contributes to risky sexual behaviour among students. The finding of the study is in keeping with the finding of Eyam et al. (2021) and Keto et al. (2020) whose studies found a strong relationship between risky sexual behaviour among students and internet use. The finding of the study is also similar with the studies of Noor (2017) and Tadele et al. (2018). These studies outlined that risky sexual behaviour among students is more correlated with internet use as it allows them to visit websites that makes them prone or exposes them to sexual contents which will in turn influence them to involve in risky sexual behavior. This is so because the internet has been reported to expose many adolescents to pornographic. However, peer pressure and other factors have been known to influence risky sexual behaviour among students as reported by many researches.

The finding of the study showed that there was a significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among students based on parents socioeconomic status. This showed that parent's socioeconomic status contributes to risky sexual behaviour among students. The finding of the study is in keeping with the finding of Eyam et al. (2021) and that of Birhan (2019). They reported that socioeconomic factors contribute immensely to risky sexual behaviour among students. The finding of this study also correlates the finding of Omisore et al. (2022) and Addis et al. (2022). The study agreed that socioeconomic factors contributes and influences behaviours especially among adolescents. This has shown that socioeconomic status is a great force in behaviour change especially among adolescents and women. This is true because studies have also supported the fact that many women of today are into prostitution and other risky sexuality because of poverty and financial issues. Hence, there is need for intervention especially among women in other to help them prevent risky sexual behaviour since most students are now into hook-ups a situation where women sell themselves or have sex for money with men and animals.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that students need intervention strategies to enhance a healthy sexual behaviour. The study further concluded that socio-demographic characteristics such as peer pressure, internet use and socioeconomic status influences risky sexual behaviour among students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Health educators should organize a sensitive sex education programs that address the unique characteristics and preferences of different student groups.
2. Curriculum experts and innovators should design school programme in such a way that sexuality education would be inclusive to address risky sexuality behaviours and improve good knowledge of human sexuality.
3. Family health education programmes should organize for parents in order to provide them with the importance of parental involvement and supportive family environments in promoting informed sexual health choices for their young growing adolescents.
4. Reproductive health educators develop a programme on the importance of tailored and well-structured sex education programs that address the diverse needs of secondary school students while considering the cultural and societal context.
5. Government through ministry of social welfare and ministry of health should develop sexuality education enhancement strategies and aimed at improving sexuality education knowledge among students through provision of appropriate approaches capable of influencing students positively in all matters related to human sexuality and reproductive health.

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